

INFLUENCE OF SHOCKWAVE ON LIGHTNING DAMAGE OF CFRP LAMINATE

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Keywords: Lightning, DIC, Damage, highspeed imaging, CFRP

ABSTRACT

This paper experimentally studied the influence of shockwave on material deformation and damage behaviour when lightning impulse current is applied. A simulated lightning high current was applied using an impulse current generator. The dynamic response of specimen subjected to lightning impulse current was measured using pair of highspeed cameras and following digital image correlation (DIC) analysis. The specimen deformation and oscillation successfully measured with good accuracy. To study difference of material, quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate and aluminium alloy sheet was tested. To understand the effect of difference of electrode condition, two different types of needle tip and with jet diverter electrode were applied. The comparison of needle type and jet diverter electrode was tested with aluminium alloy specimen and shows large difference on their dynamic response. Further, to investigate the damage effect on dynamic response of CFRP specimen, CFRP laminate without LSP protection and with protection were examined with jet diverter electrode. After lightning test, large delamination was detected by ultrasonic C-scan only from the CFRP specimen without LSP. The oscillation response of without LSP specimen shows rapid attenuation just after the first cycle, it suggests that the oscillation energy was consumed for the delamination propagation. It is concluded that the shockwave associated with applying impulse lightning current effects on the dynamic response, the internal lightning damage of CFRP laminate could be grew by material bending deformation caused by the shockwave propagation. However, the shockwave itself wouldn't initiate the lightning damage of CFRP laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) have superior mechanical and fatigue properties to a conventional metal material, therefore, newly developed recent commercial aircrafts positively adopt CFRPs to the structures in order to reduce their structural weight and maintenance cost. However, CFRP usually have inferior electrical and thermal properties to the metal material. Aircraft are occasionally struck by lightning during flight, CFRP airframe would be damaged because of their inferior electrical and thermal property if there was no appropriate lightning protection. Thus, consideration of special attention against lightning is strongly required when CFRPs are adopted to airframes.

The CFRP damage process due to lightning current are quite complicate because the several phenomena influence each other in the process such as physical, chemical and mechanical reaction [1], and they all associate in quite a short time. On that account, the lightning damage process of CFRP has yet to be clarified in detail so far.

In the past studies, lightning damage behaviour of CFRP have been investigated experimentally and numerically [2-6]. These studies basically focused on the effect of thermal-electrical interaction behaviour, chemical reaction, temperature dependent material property change, and damage propagation due to thermal strain. However, the effect of shockwave associated with an impulse lightning current would not be neglected on damage process of lightning CFRP damage. In our previous study, therefore, visualization of shockwave propagation behaviour when lightning current applied as arc entry to CFRP

laminates were examined by means of shadowgraph photography technique, the effect of electrode and material difference on shockwave propagation behaviour was reported [7]. The influence of acoustic force due to shockwave generation on material deformation and damage has yet to be studied.

In this paper, therefore, the influence of acoustic force due to shockwave associated with lightning current on material deformation and damage was experimentally studied by using high-speed digital image correlation (DIC). Two different types of electrode which having conical tip and having insulation sphere to prevent arc jet were compared to study the difference of lightning current entry condition. The lightning damage of CFRP was evaluated by non-destructive testing of using an ultrasonic scanning (UT).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material and Specimens

In this study, two different materials were experimentally tested; quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate made of uni-directional prepreg sheet of IMS60/#133 (Teijin), and conventional aluminum alloy sheet of A2024-T3. The stacking-sequence of CFRP laminate was $[45/0/-45/90]_3s$ and $[45/0/-45/90]_4s$ and their thickness was $t = 3.5\text{mm}$ and $t = 4.7\text{mm}$, respectively. Hereafter, the laminate with stacking-sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_3s$ and $[45/0/-45/90]_4s$ are referred as QI3s and QI4s, respectively. A lightning protection copper mesh (LPS) 2CU4-100FA (Dexmet Co.) was only adopted with QI4s, referred as QI4sM, in this study. The thickness of aluminum alloy sheet was 1.8mm (0.08").

Specimen was cut out from parent material in size of $500 \times 500\text{ mm}$ for both materials. To fix on the support jig with bolts, specimens have 12 of drilled hole of 8mm in diameter at even intervals on a circumference of a circle of 400 mm in diameter.

2.2 High-speed Digital Image Correlation

High-speed cameras were used for high-speed DIC measurement. In this study, ultra high-speed cameras Hyper Vision HPV-X2 (Shimadzu Corporation) and high-speed cameras Veo710 (Phantom) were adopted. HPV-X2 has high-frame rate up to 10 million fps, recording capacity of 128 frames, and 400×250 pixels resolution. In this study, the frame rate was fixed as 33,333 fps. On the other, Veo710 has capability of frame rate of 10,000 fps with resolution of 832×800 pixels and more than 1000 frames recording capacity. Hence, HPV-X2 has 3 times higher time resolution and Veo710 has 6.7 times higher spatial resolution with the setting used in this study.

An experimental setup of high-speed cameras and specimen is shown in Fig. 1. A pair of high-speed cameras are placed in reflection symmetry with the center of the specimen which is fixed as vertical to the ground using a support jig. Distance between camera to specimen surface was 1740mm. Distance between pair of cameras was 745mm for HPV-X2s and 1600mm for Veo710s, respectively. The specimen fixed on a support jig with M8 bolts as previously described. The support jig has circular window of 360mm in diameter in the center in both lightning attachment side and DIC observation (opposite to the lightning attachment) side, the both surface of specimen were exposed inside the window. The specimen surface was painted with mat-black as underlying painting to prevent harmful reflection light, subsequently painted with random speckle pattern with white paint for DIC measurement.

For DIC analysis, commercially available imaging software DaVis (LaVision Inc.) was applied in this study.

2.3 Lightning impulse current test

An impulse current generator ICG (Otowa Electric) was used to generate simulated lightning impulse current. Two types of discharge electrode, an electrode with needle tip and an electrode with jet diverter (or insulation sphere), was applied for arc entry lightning current testing (See Figure 2). Hereafter, the electrode with needle tip and the electrode with jet diverter is denoted as the needle electrode and the jet diverter electrode for a simplification in this paper. The discharge electrode was located as perpendicular to the center of the specimen surface. The gap between the electrode and the specimen surface was 2 mm for a needle electrode, 25mm for a jet diverter electrode, respectively. To ensure a certain discharge,

Figure 1: Experimental setup

a) Needle electrode

b) Jet diverter electrode

Figure 2: Discharge electrode

S/N	Material	Thickness [mm]	Peak Current [kA]	AI [A^2s]	Electrode type
AL2.0-100kA-N	A2024-T3	2.0	-98.4	520000	Needle
AL2.0-100kA-D	A2024-T3	2.0	-96.8	520000	Jet Diverter
QI4s-100kA-D	CFRP	4.7	-92.8	480000	Jet Diverter
QI3sM-100kA-D	CFRP	3.5	-96.8	520000	Jet Diverter

Table 1: Testing condition and measured lightning current parameter

initiation copper wire of 0.02 mm in diameter was attached which connected from thread of electrode rod and specimen surface. The one end of initiation wire and specimen surface was attached by using scotch tape to ensure a slight gap between them.

Testing current waveform was defined accordance with testing standard of lightning environment for commercial aircraft, SAE-ARP 5412B [8]. The component A waveform with originally having 200kA peak current was modified to 100kA.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Lightning Current Test

Resulting peak current and action integral of applied lightning current is shown in Table 1. A typical measured impulse waveform is shown in Figure 3. The waveform was measured when aluminum alloy sheet was tested with needle electrode (AL2.0-100kA-N in Table 1), its front time was $t_1 = 28.9 \mu s$ and time to half was $t_2 = 83.7 \mu s$.

a) Al-alloy, $t = 2.0$ mm, 100kA, Needle electrode (AL2.0-100kA-N)

b) Al-alloy, $t = 2.0$ mm, 100kA, Divergence electrode (AL2.0-100kA-D)

Figure 4: DIC result of displacement change of Alluminum alloy specimen center

3.2 Difference of electrode

Firstly, the influence of difference of electrode on lightning current test was examined. Two different types of electrode, needle type and jet diverter type (See Figure 2), was compared with aluminium alloy specimen.

Measured displacement history in the direction lightning current applied at center of specimen is shown in Figure 4; a) shows the result of needle electrode (AL2.0-100kA-N) and b) shows the result of jet diverter electrode (AL2.0-100kA-D), respectively. Lightning current was applied to the specimen from the electrode side and the displacement was measured form the opposite side.

The high-speed DIC result which measured the displacement change of specimen center after lightning current application shows roughly sinusoidal oscillation. The rugged waveform which can be considered as superposition of higher frequency on the principal frequency of oscillation was observed at peak of earlier oscillation phase. This is particularly noticeable in the result with needle electrode.

With needle electrode (AL2.0-100kA-N), the averaged frequency of first 11 cycles of principal frequency was 117.6 Hz. The observed frequency was change as a time goes by, the first cycle frequency was 153.8 Hz, the second cycle frequency was 126.6 Hz, and average frequency of third to 11th cycle was 112.6 Hz. The maximum amplitude of oscillation was appeared in the first cycle, the amplitude was 2.43 mm though the maximum deformation of 2.88 mm was observed in 4th cycle. As shown in Fig 4 a), the oscillation center was varied over time, the travel of oscillation center shift converged in about 1.5 mm after 10th cycle.

With jet diverter electrode (AL2.0-100kA-D), the averaged frequency of first 11 cycles of principal frequency was 127.5 Hz. As same as test result with needle electrode, the observed frequency was

Figure 5: Comparison of specimen damage at lightning current attached location of aluminum alloy specimen tested with different electrode.

Figure 6: Comparison of shockwave propagation behavior associated with applying impulse current on aluminum alloy sheet with different electrode visualized by shadowgraph method [7]

change as time passed. The first and 5th cycle frequency was 192.3 Hz and 128.2 Hz, respectively. The latter averaged frequency from 6th to 11th cycles was 111.5 Hz. The maximum amplitude of oscillation was observed in the first cycle, the amplitude was 3.53 mm. the maximum deformation of 3.80 mm was observed in third cycle. The oscillation center was varied over time as same as needle electrode, the travel of oscillation center converged in about 0.57 mm after 10th cycle.

Though the condition of applied impulse current was identical, measured oscillation response was largely different with difference of type of electrode. The strong effect of superposition of higher frequency on the principal oscillation was observed when needle electrode was applied. On the other, the limited effect of higher frequency in the first few cycles at peak and valley when jet diverter electrode was applied. The difference of electrode type resulted in the difference of the damage at lightning current attached point. The magnified view of damage at specimen surface is compared in Fig 5. With the needle electrode, attachment of thermal spraying metal from electrode in circular form was observed (Figure 5 a)). On the other, only small thermal damage was observed the specimen tested with jet diverter electrode (Figure 5 b)). Adopting the insulation spare of jet diverter electrode could efficiently avoid arc jet generation and resulting damage on the specimen. It is considered that the splaying metal attachment form needle electrode due to arc jet affect the oscillation behaviour, resulting in the superposed higher oscillation of aluminium alloy specimen.

Focusing on the amplitude of the oscillation, larger amplitude of oscillation was observed with the jet diverter electrode. It is considered that impact force generated by shock wave was different between needle electrode and jet diverter electrode, jet diverter electrode generates larger acoustic force. On the other, larger travel of oscillation center occurred with the needle electrode. The possible cause of this result is a plastic deformation of material due to applied impact force and a temporally deformation of material due to pressure difference between electrode side and opposite side of specimen. The specimen deformation after impulse current test was carefully examined by visual inspection, any residual deformation was not observed. The cause of the travel of oscillation center, therefore, could be a pressure fluctuation caused by shockwave generation at the lightning attached side of specimen. The difference of shockwave propagation behaviour between needle electrode and jet diverter electrode which visualized with shadowgraph method is compared in Fig. 6 [7]. As shown in the figure, shockwave propagation behaviour is largely different with applied electrode. This difference of shockwave behaviour could have effect on the oscillation response. The lightning impulse current with needle electrode generate a shorter and lower impulse force and larger pressure witch result in lower amplitude

of oscillation and larger travel of oscillation center. On the other, with jet diverter electrode generate a longer and higher impulse force and smaller pressure witch result in higher amplitude of oscillation and smaller travel of oscillation center.

3.3 Effect of CFRP damage on oscillation response

The measured displacement history of center of the CFRP specimen without LSP (QI4s-100kA-D) and with LSP (QI3sM-100kA-D) obtained by DIC when lightning impulse current was applied are shown in Fig 7. In this comparison, both specimens were tested using jet diverter electrode. Both results showed sinusoidal oscillation, however, sharp peak and valley was observed in first several cycles. Comparing with the result of aluminum alloy specimen, larger damping of oscillation was obtained for both CFRP specimens.

The result of CFRP specimen without LSP (QI4s-100kA-D) shows the 368.4 Hz or principal averaged frequency of first 9 cycles. The oscillation frequency slightly changes over time, the frequency of the first cycle was 416.7 Hz, and average frequency from second to 9th cycle was 362.3 Hz. The both maximum amplitude of oscillation and maximum displacement was 5.04mm which observed in first cycle. Though the travel of oscillation center was slightly observed, the deflection itself was much smaller than that of aluminum alloy and the travel was converged after 0.05 s from lightning current application.

a) CFRP $t=4.7$ mm, 100kA, with jet diverter electrode (QI4s-100kA-D)

b) CFRP $t = 4.7$ mm, 100 kA, with jet diverter electrode (QI3sM-100kA-D)

Figure 7: DIC result of displacement change of CFRP specimen center

The result of CFRP specimen with LSP (QI3sM-100kA-D) shows the 289.88 Hz of principal averaged frequency of first 9 cycles. The obvious oscillation frequency changes over time was not confirmed. The frequency of first cycle was 285.7 Hz. The maximum amplitude of oscillation and maximum displacement was 3.69mm which observed in the first cycle. As same as the without LSP specimen, slight travel of oscillation center was observed, and the deflection was converged after 0.05s from lightning current application.

The damaged surface of CFRP specimen after lightning current test is shown in Fig. 8. The result of both CFRP specimen without LSP and with LSP is shown in Fig. 8 a) and b), respectively. As shown in the figure (Figure 8 a)), fiber breakage, ply lift in surface fiber direction, and surrounding resin deterioration damage propagate in direction of orthogonal to surface fiber direction was observed center of specimen where lightning current attached when CFRP specimen without LSP was tested. On the other, only the melting and vaporized damage of copper mesh LSP was occurred on CFRP specimen with LPS after lightning test (Figure 8 b)).

Ultrasonic C-scan was conducted to evaluate the internal damage of CFRP specimens. A high frequency ultrasonic flaw detector HIS-3-HF (Krautkramer GmbH) with 3.5 MHz transducer was adopted in this study. The results are shown in Figure 9. After lightning test, large delamination was observed in CFRP specimen without LSP (QI4s-100kA-D) (See Figure 9 a)). The result UT shows that the internal damage of the CFRP specimen without LSP consists of several delamination which form spiral shape damage correspondence with the fiber orientation of each layer. The delamination location was limited to the vicinity of specimen surface where lightning current attached. On the other, the UT result shows that applying copper mesh LSP can efficiently prevent generating internal damage of CFRP specimen (See Figure 9 b)).

a) CFRP specimen without LSP (QI4s-100kA-D)

b) CFRP specimen with LSP (QI3sM-100kA-D)

Figure 8: CFRP specimen surface after lightning test, 100kA, with jet diverter electrode

a) CFRP specimen without LSP (QI4s-100kA-D)

b) CFRP specimen with LSP (QI3sM-100kA-D)

Figure 9: Ultrasonic C-scan result of CFRP specimen after lightning test, 100kA, with jet diverter electrode

In the previous study [2, 4], the main cause of lightning damage of CFRP was explained as follows; At the beginning, high temperature of arc root and joule heating caused by lightning current rise temperature of lightning attached point, carbon fiber sublimation and fiber breakage occur. Subsequently, surrounding matrix resin is rapidly vaporized and evaporated resin gas explosively expand, then the interlaminar delamination occur. The result obtained in this study can also explain the damage mechanism previously noted. The both CFRP specimen with LSP and without LSP was tested with identical condition of lightning current, and both specimens showed similar oscillatory response. However, delamination damage was occurred only in the CFRP specimen without LSP, any delamination was not observed in the CFRP specimen with LSP. This result simply indicates that the acoustic force due to shockwave associate with lightning current and resulting oscillatory deformation was not a main cause initiating the CFRP lightning damage.

Though the thickness of specimen without LSP (QI4s-100kA-D) was thicker than that with LSP (QI3sM-100kA-D), the measured maximum amplitude was thinner specimen (QI3sM-100kA-D). And sharp decrease of amplitude was observed after latter half of the first cycle. These facts suggest that the large and rugged peak of first cycle of oscillation observed in CFRP specimen without LSP was associated with the damage initiation of CFRP and resulting bending deformation grew the internal delamination which initiated by joule heating and evaporated resin gas. After large peak of first cycle of oscillation, rapid attenuation of amplitude of oscillation was observed. It is considered that the oscillation energy was consumed for the delamination propagation, the amplitude of oscillation was rapidly decreased.

The oscillation response of CFRP specimen with LSP showed smooth attenuations of amplitude. Since no delamination was occurred inside the specimen, the energy did not consume for the damage propagation, it is considered that most of the energy applied by the acoustic force due to shockwave generation could be consumed for specimen oscillation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The dynamic response of aluminum alloy and CFRP specimen caused by acoustic force due to shockwave generation when lightning current attached was experimentally studied in this paper. The high-speed DIC technique was successfully applied to measure dynamic response of lightning struck specimens. Obtained conclusions are as follows;

- The shockwave associated with applying lightning current have influence on the dynamic response of both aluminum alloy and CFRP laminate. The specimen after lightning current applied shows sinusoidal oscillation. The amplitude and the frequency are differs depending on the materials and testing condition.
- Difference of electrode type had influence on dynamic response of aluminum alloy sheet. With the needle electrode without jet diverter, thermal spraying metal from the electrode is attached to the specimen surface, resulting oscillation shows rugged waveform with superposition of higher frequency.
- Though the acoustic force due to shockwave generation is not a major cause of CFRP internal damage, the bending deformation caused by shockwave could grew the delamination which are initiated by joule heating and subsequent explosive resin evaporation due to intensive lightning current. If the LSP could effectively avoid the lightning current flow in to inside of CFRP, the bending deformation and oscillation due to shockwave associate with lightning current do not generate the internal CFRP damage.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am grateful to Mr. Koji Sawaki of Nagoya Univ., Mr. Katsunori Takita, Ms. Junko Aoki of IHI Jet Service Co. and Mr. Shintaro Kamiyama of Graduate student of Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology for technical support. This work is supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number 17K14881.

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